

Boron Trifluoride Dietherate Complex—a Better Condensing Agent for the Synthesis of Some 4-Phenyl coumarins

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In course of our investigations of some natural 4-phenyl coumarins^{2,3} we were interested to obtain 5 : 7-dihydroxy-4-phenyl coumarin^{3,4} which could readily be obtained by Pechman condensation of phloroglucinol with ethyl benzoyl acetate using H₂SO₄ or P₂O₅ as condensing agents the yields of which are not reported in the literature. Precedence of poor yield of 4-phenyl coumarins using H₂SO₄ as condensing agent in Pechman reaction is also provided by the work of Robertson and Sandrock⁵. They reported that *p*-cresol and ethyl benzoyl acetate reacted in presence of H₂SO₄ to give 4-phenyl-6-methyl coumarin in a very poor yield (2%). The instability of the β -keto esters in presence of H₂SO₄ or P₂O₅ may be a factor in the poor yields of these 4-phenyl coumarins. Boron trifluoride dietherate complex was considered a better condensing agent in these cases, in view of its use in the synthesis of 4-methyl coumarin by Shah and Shah⁶.

In the present communication we report the synthesis of three phenolic 4-phenyl coumarins using boron trifluoride dietherate as condensing agent.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The appropriate phenol (1 mole) and ethyl benzoyl acetate (1 mole) was dissolved in minimum amount of acetic acid. Boron trifluoride dietherate (2 mole) was added slowly to the above solution with constant stirring at 0°–5°. The reaction mixture was kept for 72 hr. and then poured into crushed ice (100 g) when a precipitate was obtained. The precipitate was filtered, dried and recrystallised from aqueous alcohol when the appropriate 4-phenyl coumarin was obtained. The crude product was purified by chromatography over silica gel in every case. The homogeneity of the compounds were examined by t.l.c. using a mixture of benzene : methanol : acetic acid in proportions 19 : 1 : 1.4. The data are reported in table below.

TABLE

Phenolic substrate	Condensing agent	Product	Yield %	M.P. °C	R _f
Phloroglucinol	Boron trifluoride dietherate complex	5 : 7-dihydroxy 4-phenyl coumarin	25	234–35	0.26
Pyrogallol	„	7 : 8-dihydroxy 4-phenyl coumarin	25	188–89	0.50
Resorcinol	„	7-hydroxy-4-phenyl coumarin	30	241–43	0.59

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R E F E R E N C E S

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